

Inhibition effect of histidine and related compounds on corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution

Ranu Banerjee, Ranjana and M. M. Nandi*

Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Durgapur-713 209, West Bengal, India

E-mail : murarimohan_nandi@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received online 05 July 2012, revised 14 September 2012, accepted 17 September 2012

Abstract : The inhibition effect of histidine (1), *N*-benzenesulphonylhistidine (2), *N*-benzenesulphonyl histamine (3), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)propionic acid (4) and α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)propionic acid (5) towards the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M sodium chloride solution has been studied using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order : 1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5. The inhibition efficiency of 5 is the highest, which reaches 91.5–94.3%. This may be due to the presence of more basic tetrahydropyrimidine group.

Keywords : Brass, EIS, polarisation, histidine, histamine, imidazoline, tetrahydropyrimidine.

Introduction

Amino acids and their derivatives are of particular importance as corrosion inhibitors because they are environmentally friendly and have very low toxicity^{1–10}.

Recently extensive work is going on the inhibition effect of various amino acids on copper and steel in HCl, HNO₃ and H₂SO₄^{11–14} media. Zhang and coworkers studied the inhibition effect of copper corrosion in 0.5 M HCl solution by aspartic acid, asparagine, glutamic acid and glutamine¹¹ which act as mixed type inhibitor. In order to introduce non toxic organic inhibitor for copper in acidic chloride solution, cysteine was used by Ismail¹. Inhibition efficiency was 84%. Presence of Cu²⁺ ion increases the inhibition efficiency to 90%. Glycine, alanine, tyrosine are also found to be good corrosion inhibitors in acidic media^{15–17}. Looking for environmentally acceptable corrosion inhibitors for brass in marine environment, we have chosen histidine (1) and prepared *N*-benzenesulphonylhistidine (2), *N*-benzenesulphonyl histamine (3), α -benzenesulphonamido- β -(2-imidazolynyl)propionic acid (4) and α -benzenesulphonamido- β -2-(1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidinyl)propionic acid (5). Two electrochemical techniques potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy have been used to study the effect of the addition of these com-

pounds on the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The chemical composition of the commercial brass used in the present study was 59.8% Cu, 40.0% Zn and traces of Fe and Pb. The working electrode for potentiodynamic study and EIS measurement was prepared from the brass rod from which only the circular cross section (0.25 cm²) of rod was exposed. The brass sample was properly polished.

Then the samples were degreased with AR grade ethanol and acetone and rinsed with double distilled water prior to each experiment.

L-Histidine (Merck) was used after recrystallization. The compound 2 was prepared by following usual procedure described in our earlier communication¹⁸. Compound 3 was prepared by condensation of histamine dihydrochloride with benzenesulphonyl chloride at 40 °C. Histamine dihydrochloride (5 g) was treated with 20 ml 10% NaOH solution and 4 ml benzenesulphonyl chloride and the mixture was kept on magnetic stirrer at 40 °C for 20 min. White compound was separated. It was recrystallized from hot water. Compounds (4 and 5) were prepared

by heating a mixture of *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-aspartic acid¹⁹ and ethylene diamine or propylene diamine in 1 : 2 mole ratio at 130–160 °C for 8 h in air atmosphere. The fused mass was extracted with water (pH ~ 10). Compounds were isolated from the filtrate by extraction with ether. These were recrystallized from aqueous DMSO.

Fig. 1 shows the molecular structure of the investigated compounds and their inhibition efficiency. Analytical data of the derivatives are given in Table 1. The pH measurements were made with an Orion 420A Plus pH meter using 9157BN Triode pH electrode. The pH meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and bo-

rax buffer solution in water. The aggressive environment used was 0.6 *M* aqueous NaCl solution prepared from AR grade reagent and double distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0. Oxygen content of the sodium chloride solution was 7.3 mg/L. All other reagents were of AR quality.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out with polished and degreased brass specimens having an exposed surface area of 0.25 cm². The electrochemical measurements were carried out in a standard three-electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml.

Structure of the compounds	Inhibition efficiency (%)		
	Tafel extrapolation method	EIS	Average method
<p>1</p>	60.7	64.7	62.7
<p>2</p>	71.6	75.2	73.4
<p>3</p>	80.7	82.5	81.6
<p>4</p>	86.8	89.9	88.4
<p>5</p>	91.5	94.3	92.3

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the inhibitors and their inhibition efficiency.

Table 1 . Analytical data of the inhibitors

Inhibitors	% Yield (m.p. °C)	Analysis (%) :		
		C	H	N
2	60	48.50	4.35	14.35
	(267)	(48.81)	(4.40)	(14.24)
3	65	52.35	4.95	16.40
	(150)	(52.59)	(5.18)	(16.73)
4	10	48.46	5.00	13.99
	(208)	(48.48)	(5.05)	(14.14)
5	9	50.25	5.95	13.25
	(152)	(50.16)	(6.10)	(13.50)

The counter electrode was a platinum plate with 1 cm² surface area, the reference electrode consisted of a commercial saturated calomel electrode with a Luggin capillary bridge and the working electrode was made up of brass. Polarization studies were carried out using potentiostat/galvanostat (ACM Instruments Gill AC) and the data obtained were analyzed using the software "ACM Instruments version 5". The degreased working electrode was immersed in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution and allowed to stabilize for 30 min²⁰. The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass specimen in the test solution with and without inhibitors were recorded at a scan rate of 1 mV/s in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution (pH 6) at 30 ± 0.5 °C. The inhibition efficiencies of the compounds were determined from corrosion current density using the Tafel extrapolation method.

Electrochemical AC impedance studies :

AC impedance measurements were conducted at room temperature using "ACM Instruments Gill AC". The instruments were controlled by the software "ACM Instruments version 5" between 1 mHz and 100 kHz. An AC sinusoid voltage of ~ ±10 mV was applied at corrosion potential (E_{corr}). The brass sample with an exposing surface area of 0.25 cm² was used as the working electrode. A three electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml with a platinum plate electrode and a saturated calomel electrode was used²¹.

Results and discussion

The ability of an organic molecule to inhibit metal corrosion depends on several factors and some of them are the shape, aromaticity, bond strength to metal sub-

strate, the presence of heteroatom and number of bonding atoms or groups²²⁻²⁵. Temperature, pH and stability in the aggressive media are also factors related to the efficiency of the inhibitor²⁶⁻³¹. All compounds are stable in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution. Room temperature 30 ± 0.5 °C was selected for inhibition studies. Experiments carried out at pH 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 using *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine³² by weight loss method. It has been observed that inhibition efficiency is maximum in between pH 6 to 8 and pH 6 is selected for these studies. Concentration of chloride ion in sea water is 0.54. Hence 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution is chosen.

Compounds having three nitrogen atoms in an aromatic ring are reported to be effective inhibitors for many metals and alloys³³. Benzotriazole and its derivatives offer a good protection against corrosion of brass^{34,35}. But these compounds are toxic. We have chosen L-histidine and histamine which contain three nitrogen atoms in the molecule as starting material and prepared *N*-benzenesulphonyl derivatives. At pH 6 inhibition efficiency of L-histidine is 60.7%. After introducing C₆H₅SO₂ group inhibition efficiency is increased by 10.9%.

Compound 3 was found to be better inhibitor and the inhibition efficiency with a concentration of 0.04 mM is the highest at the room temperature, which reaches 80.7%. Compounds 2 and 3 are better inhibitors than *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine³² due to more basic character and presence of three nitrogen atoms³³.

N-Benzenesulphonyl glycine (I.E. = 45.6)

If the imidazole group of 2 is replaced by more basic imidazoline or tetrahydropyridine group, the resultant molecules exhibits better inhibition activity.

4 (I.E. = 88.4)

5 (I.E. = 92.90)

Fig. 2. Effect of 1 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 3. Effect of 2 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution with varying concentration of 1 to 5 were recorded and are shown in the Figs. 2-

6. The potentiodynamic polarization parameters are listed in Table 2. Inhibition efficiencies³⁶ are calculated following usual procedure³². All reagent show relatively same behavior against the polarization and the profile of the

Fig. 4. Effect of 3 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 5. Effect of 4 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

anodic and cathodic curves are not changed, indicating that the inhibitory merely block the reaction sites of metal surface without affecting the anodic and cathodic reac-

tion mechanism. With increasing inhibitor concentration, no obvious trend is observed in the shift of E_{corr} values suggesting that these compounds behave as mixed type

Fig. 6. Effect of 5 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Table 2. The electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency values for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	E_{corr} (mV vs SCE)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	I.E. (%)
	0	-301.8	6.14	
1	4×10^{-4}	-246.7	2.50	59.2
1	4×10^{-5}	-230.6	2.41	60.7
1	4×10^{-6}	-256.0	2.79	54.5
2	4×10^{-4}	-267.8	1.88	69.3
2	4×10^{-5}	-257.5	1.74	71.6
2	4×10^{-6}	-239.9	1.97	67.9
3	4×10^{-4}	-252.6	1.38	77.5
3	4×10^{-5}	-241.3	1.18	80.7
3	4×10^{-6}	-256.4	1.55	74.7
4	4×10^{-4}	-235.4	0.96	84.3
4	4×10^{-5}	-215.8	0.81	86.8
4	4×10^{-6}	-258.0	1.14	81.4
5	4×10^{-3}	-241.6	0.99	83.8
5	4×10^{-4}	-210.4	0.52	91.5
5	4×10^{-5}	-226.3	0.79	84.3

Table 3. The impedance measurements and inhibition efficiency values of sulphonamido derivatives for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	R_{ct} (K ohm)	C_{dl} (F)	I.E. (R_{ct}) (%)
	0	0.358	2.38×10^{-4}	
1	4×10^{-4}	0.923	1.06×10^{-4}	61.2
1	4×10^{-5}	1.016	8.33×10^{-5}	64.7
1	4×10^{-6}	0.823	2.01×10^{-4}	56.5
2	4×10^{-4}	1.339	1.82×10^{-4}	73.2
2	4×10^{-5}	1.445	1.48×10^{-4}	75.2
2	4×10^{-6}	1.201	5.07×10^{-5}	70.1
3	4×10^{-4}	1.792	1.60×10^{-5}	80.0
3	4×10^{-5}	2.056	9.10×10^{-5}	82.5
3	4×10^{-6}	1.657	1.86×10^{-4}	78.3
4	4×10^{-4}	3.442	4.13×10^{-5}	89.5
4	4×10^{-5}	3.569	1.38×10^{-4}	89.9
4	4×10^{-6}	2.516	2.13×10^{-4}	85.7
5	4×10^{-3}	2.505	2.10×10^{-5}	85.7
5	4×10^{-4}	6.329	3.54×10^{-5}	94.3
5	4×10^{-5}	2.801	4.87×10^{-5}	87.2

inhibitors.

Electrochemical AC impedance studies :

The effects of the reagents on the impedance behavior of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution were recorded.

These Nyquist plots reveal that the impedance response of the brass has significantly changed after using these inhibitors. Various impedance parameters such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), double layer capacitance (C_{dl})

and inhibition efficiency (IE) are given in Table 3. The charge transfer values are calculated from the difference in impedance at lower and higher frequencies as suggested by Narayana *et al.*³⁷.

The IE is calculated following usual procedure³⁸. There is a good agreement between the obtained from polarization and impedance studies (Tables 2–3).

The inhibition efficiency of histidine is in the range of 60.7–64.7%. It increased by 10% after introduction of C₆H₅ group in **2**. The inhibition efficiency is further improved (88–94%) by replacing imidazole group with more basic imidazoline and tetrahydropyrimidine group.

Conclusion :

- (i) All investigated compounds have shown inhibiting properties for brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution.
- (ii) The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the compounds increases in the following order : **1 < 2 < 3 < 4 < 5**.
- (iii) About 10% improvement in the inhibition property of histidine is observed by introducing C₆H₅-group. Further improvement is achieved when imidazole group is replaced by more basic imidazoline or tetrahydropyrimidine group.

References

1. K. M. Ismail, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2007, **52**, 7811.
2. Z. Ghasemi and A. Tizpar, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2006, **252**, 3667.
3. D. Q. Zhang, L. X. Gao and G. D. Zhou, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2005, **35**, 1081.
4. O. Olivares, N. V. Likhanova, B. Gomez, J. Navarrate, M. E Llanos-Serrano, E. Arce and J. M. Hallen, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2006, **252**, 2894.
5. W. A. Badawy, K. M. Ismail and A. M. Fathi, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2006, **51**, 4182.
6. H. Ashassi-Sorkhabia, M. R. Majidib and K. Seyyedi, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2004, **225**, 176.
7. H. Ashassi-Sorkhabi, Z. Ghasemi and D. Seifzadeh, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2005, **249**, 408.
8. E. E. Oguzie, Y. Li and F. H. Wang, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2007, **310**, 90.
9. G. Moretti and F. Guidi, *Corros. Sci.*, 2002, **44**, 1995.
10. D. Q. Zhang, L. X. Gao and G. D. Zhou, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2005, **35**, 1081.
11. D. Q. Zhang, Q. R. Cai, X. M. He, L. X. Gao and G. D. Zhou, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 2008, **112**, 353.
12. D. Zhang, Q. Cai, X. He, Li Gao and G. S. Kim, 2008.
13. D. Zhang, B. Xie, Li Gao, Q. Cai, H. Joo and K. Y. Lu, *Thin Solid Film*, 2011.
14. M. A. Amin, Q. Mohsen, K. F. Khaled and H. Arida, *Corros. Sci.*, 2010, **52**, 1684.
15. M. A. Amin, S. S. Abd El Rahim and H. T. M. Abdel-Fatah, *Corros. Sci.*, 2009, **51**, 882.
16. M. A. Amine and K. F. Khaled, *Corros. Sci.*, 2010, **52**, 1684.
17. K. Bayoumi, L. Bazzi, R. Salghi, M. Mihit, B. Hammouti, A. Albourine and S. El Issami, *Materials Letter*, 2008, **62**, 3325.
18. M. M. Nandi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 809.
19. Ranjana and M. M. Nandi, *Indian J Chem. Tech.*, 2011, **18**, 29.
20. G. Petkova, E. Sokolova and P. Ivanov, *Brit. Corros. J.*, 1996, **31**, 55.
21. R. Gasparac, C. R. Martin, E. Stupnisek-Lisac and Z. Mandic, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2000, **147**, 991.
22. W. Qafsaqui, Ch. Blanc, N. Pebere, A. Srhiri and G. Mankowski, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2000, **30**, 959.
23. E. Szocs, G. Vastag, A. Shaban and E. Kalman, *Corros. Sci.*, 2005, **47**, 893.
24. W. Mok, A. Jenkins and C. Gamble, *Corros. Sci.*, 2003, **6**, 1.
25. S. Ramesh and S. Rajeswari, *Corros. Sci.*, 2005, **42**, 161.
26. D. Thomans, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1998, **145**, L42.
27. Y. C. Wu, P. Zhang and H. W. Pickering, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1993, **140**, 2791.
28. T. Notoya and G. W. Poling, *Corros.*, 1976, **32**, 216.
29. Y. Ling, Y. Guan and K. N. Han, *Corros.*, 1976, **32**, 216.
30. H. Ma, S. Chen, B. Yin, S. Zhao and X. Liu, *Corros. Sci.*, 2003, **45**, 867.
31. D. Zhang, L. Gao and G. Zhou, *Corros. Sci.*, 2004, **16**, 3031.
32. R. Banerjee, M. M. Nandi and Ranjana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1389.

33. M. Finsgar, A. Lesar, A. Kokalj and I. Milosev, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2008, **53**, 8287.
34. R. Ravichandran and N. Rajendran, *Appl. Surface Sci.*, 2005, **241**, 449; 2005, **239**, 186.
35. Z. Mountassir and A. Sehiri, *Corros. Sci.*, 2007, **49**, 1352.
36. E. Khamis, E. S. H. El-Ashry and A. K. Ibrahim, *Brit. Corros. J.*, 2000, **35**, 150.
37. S. Haruyama, T. Tsuru and B. Gijutsu, *J. Jpn. Soc. Corros. Eng.*, 1978, **27**, 573.
38. M. A. Qurashi and R. Sardar, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2003, **33**, 1163.